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Session 3 live-captioning, Wednesday, 21 June 2023:

[Surveys within the Milky Way and nearby galaxies](#)

Matthew Hosek: Revealing the Large-Scale Kinematic Structure of the Galactic Center with the Roman Space Telescope

I hope you're well rested and excited for a day of talks. Today between 11:30 and 12:00, we have a discussion session, seven topics. You can sign up on Slack. There are groups in prison. If you pick a topic on the topics are on Slack, than in person you can follow those lovely printouts and go sit with your friends and talk about those topics. One of the topics is a choose your own adventure so if you want to not do any of those per to something else, go there. Thank you. Welcome, Matthew Hosek, who will be talking about the galactic center.

Matt: Thanks to the organizers were giving me the opportunity to speak today. My name is a Matt Hosek I'm a post-doc and brings an price of a look at the UCLA Galactic group. I like to talk about some of the exciting opportunities the Roman Space Telescope will give us to study the Milky Way galactic center. For the purposes of the store, and is a galactic center, in referring to the region that extends up to a radius of 150 parsecs from the central supermassive black. This region are sometimes referred to as the central molecular zone. It contains a part of 80% of other dense molecular gas in the entire galaxy in this region. At a distance of just 8,000 parsecs from our sun, our galactic center is 100 times closer than any other galactic nucleus. That means it's the only galactic nucleus for which we can study the stars in a resort manner and in high detail. When we see our galactic center, we find that it is amazingly complex with many different components and features. For example, at the very center, we have Sagittarius a start, our central supermassive black hole that is 400 million times the mass of hours in pair any gravitational potential within Central has parsecs of the galaxy or so. The rest of the region is dominated by two main stellar structures. The nuclear star cluster or NSC which is the densest and most massive star cluster in our galaxy with 10 million solar masses within a radius of 5 parsecs. The nuclear stellar disk which is a more extended structure of about 1 billion solar masses that is elongated along the galactic plane and we just do a radius of about 100 parsecs or so. Both of these populations are old star populations with ages of about 5 to 10000000000 years old. There is more than just old stars at the galactic center. There's also many examples of recent and ongoing star formation. The galactic center is one of the most actively star-forming

regions of our galaxy today. 2 prominent examples of that activity are shown here. The arches and interpret clusters paired with ages less than 5 million years old and masses of 10,000 solar masses or so, these two clusters are among the most massive young clusters in the galaxy. Why do we care? When you look at galactic nuclei in other galaxies, especially those in other spiral galaxies, we find that they share many of these same features and characteristics. We see central supermassive black holes and nuclear star clusters and disks and young clusters. What that tells us is that our galactic center serves as a valuable template for understanding the evolution and formation of galactic nuclei. Again, the galactic center is the only place where we can study these features in very high detail. For example, we can measure the proper motion. GWC has been very, very exciting with its high sensitivity, spatial resolution and wavelength coverage. It will have enabled many new investigations of the galactic center. By my count, there is something like nine ongoing GWC programs in the region. Programs are still ongoing but they cover a wide variety of topics. Some including star formation. How do stars formed in the galactic center to make what are the gas property? What are the details of the stellar populations at the very center of the galaxy connect the kinematics, density profiles, and so forth. These programs are suffered village clustered around the highest density or highest extinction regions to the galactic center which is what JWST with its fantastic capabilities really makes it. Looking at this, you'll see that in terms of spatial coverage, JWST can really only observe a small region of the galactic center as a whole. That is shown here. These silent boxes represent the NIRCam a and B models. You can observe the small region is very high details, it's hard to get a picture of the large-scale structure of the region. This is especially true if we want to measure proper motions which would require multiple observations across the entire region. This is more Roman can come in. With just five-point things of the wide Field instrument, you can image the entire -- nearly the entire galactic center region. With a chastity resolution and precision. That makes Brahmin uniquely suited for large-scale dynamical studies of the galactic center. We can measure proper motions are two radii of 150 parsecs from Sagittarius a star. We are starting to reach skills are we observe these and other galaxies but we have all the details, proper motion information. To quantify this a bit further, this is a plot of number of stars observed as a function of the observed area for current proper motion surveys of the galactic center compares to what we can do with Robin. The black points found here, these are proper motion surveys taken from the ground. When you observe from the ground, we have to correct from the turbulence of the Earth's atmosphere to get the spatial resolution. The penalty you pay for that is that you are really only able to get astrometry over a relatively small view of field. That's why the ground-based surveys are focused on the lower left part. We do better when we go up to a chastity with these blue points because now we are above the atmosphere and we can get precise astrometry of a much larger field within a single pointing. The registrar's job is what Roman can do. The five pointing galactic center must say, we expected we can measure the proper motions of 16.5 million stars in the region and cover an area that's at least ten times larger than any other proper motion survey. We know from our experience with a chastity that Roman can deliver high precision astrometry at the galactic center. we can measure specific stellar positions with an accuracy of 0.15 to 0.4 Valley Art second. A journal astrophysics of the epics of observation over five years, that means we can measure proper motions to a procession of 50 to 100 microseconds per year. This gets even more impressive when we consider just taking if just one of the field, the Center must feel and add it as part of the galactic

bulge time domain survey. Which we talked about yesterday. Because of the high cadence of these observations, we expect that we will be able to get proper motion perception of three micro-arc seconds per year. 0.15 kilometers per second which is really incredible. In fact, adding the galactic center to the time domain survey would enable a host of science cases, not just those driven by dynamics and if you're interested, I encourage you to take a look at the paper that John Terry, myself, and our collaborators recently did which should be posted soon. At the very end, just wanted to highlight to science cases which I think nicely shows the synergy between JWST and Roman. The first one is the formation and evolution of galactic nuclei. In particular, this NSC and NSD structures I mentioned earlier. With JWST, we can characterize the stellar population, we can go really deep of a specific regions and we can ask questions like what triggers or suppresses star formation at the galactic center? What is the star formation history of the NSC and NSD? We come in with Roman with this large real kinematics are where we can ask questions like what is the kinematic structure of the NSD and the NSC? What is the relationship and what does this indicate about their formation? We can also ask what is the total mass distribution gimmick and gravitational potential in the galactic center region? Something that is surprisingly uncertain. In order to answer this question, we need proper motions coverage of the largest expanse of these structures that we can do. This is really in the Roman regime. The second science case I want to spring up was studying the life cycle of star clusters at the galactic center back the arches and quintuplet. These clusters are only expected to deliver 10 to 20000000 years before they get tidally disrupted. Even at that young age, they are expected to have large tidal tails. With JWST, we can characterize the stellar formation of the formations themselves, we can ask questions such as what is the stellar initial mass function of star clusters at the galactic center? Investor evidence that low mass star formation is suppressed in this region, possibly due to the extreme star-forming environment? With Roman, looking at these clusters, we get the larger scale kinematic view. We can look for, detect and characterize for the first time these tidal tails. We can ask her to star clusters evolve and dissolve in galactic nuclei? Do they actually follow what the models predict what happen? We can also ask how has this tidal stripping impacted the observed cluster population that we see today? This tidal stripping a something we're going to have to take into account if we really want to properly derive the initial mass function from our JWST observations. Just to finish up, I would say I'm very excited. I think Roman will enable a new era a sign that our galactic center. I hope I've convinced you that Roman is uniquely suited to do a large-scale dynamic study of the galactic center. We are talking about the proper motions of 16.5 million stars in this region. Roman will really provide a large-scale dynamical context for many of the really exciting studies going on at the galactic center with JWST and other instruments. With that, I can take your questions and thank you very much.

Is there any questions in the room? Lets go online while the microphone gets out there. Nothing online. You are up. Matt: That's an excellent question. do folks online here the question as well or do I have to repeat it? Just making sure. Perfect. Excellent question. Turns out at the galactic center, we can actually use diocese stars to define our reference frame, to define that coordinate system. Gaia can see stars at the galactic center directly. It can observe stars in the foreground. There have been several projects, some led by myself, some by others, that have used Gaia foreground stars to absolute astronomy from observations of the galactic center. The

answer is thus preferences sources do already exist. We don't have the background quasars but Gaia does a very good job of defining the reference frame. Great. Any other questions in the room? Do you see a role for the spectroscopy mode in the galactic center? Matt: The spectroscopy mode. That's a resolution of 600 or -- Theirs are 300 and then there is a high resolution. Just wondering. Matt: It's a good question. I haven't thought about the spectroscopy mode that much. And the honest and have to think about it more. For the Center must region, but we are characterizing stars, a day old, at a young? What are the property is usually require a spectral resolution of 3,000 or 4,000 using of Cyprus on tech. Have to think a little bit more, but it's a great question. What could be used with solar spectroscopy? I'd have to think about that. Take a quick question. If getting distance is going to be a problem, do you really need kilometers per second, your proper motions but to convert them to velocities. Matt: That number was assuming a distance of 8,000 parsecs. That's the average star at the galactic center. When we are pointing towards the galactic center, the density of stars is so high that they will dominate the field. There is some foreground. We can do cuts to remove them. There's definitely some distance dispersion. That is part of a point of uncertainty. A lot of these stars are around that 8,000 parsecs distance. That's where those numbers came from. Because I think that's about time for the session. Remaining questions continue in the slack. Great, thank you.

Ankita Mondal: The origin of the very metal-rich stars near the Sun

The next talk will be a recording. Ankita will talk about the origin of metal which stars near the sun. For this, there is one other recorded session. In this session. For both of those, we'll show the recording and then go to the next answer at questions in the slack and they will answer them as their time zone permits. Ankita: Hello, everyone. My name is a Ankita Mondal and I am a MSc graduate from India. I will be presenting before you in brief about my current research project on the origin of matter which stars near the center supervised by professional Kenneth Freeman and Dr. Michael Hayden. Understanding the evolution of our Galaxy Milky Way is one of the major challenges of astronomy. A loss for detailed studies of its structure, star formation history and chemical composition. Thus providing valuable insights into the process. The Galaxy archeology, used fossil records of the stars that have been born throughout the history of the Milky Way to figure out how it has evolved over the ages. The stars near the sun show the white point of complex stages in this region near the sun but returned as the solar neighborhood contains stars spending a huge age and metallicity about which I'll be talking in the coming few slides. Coming to our main topic that is the super soldier star problem in the solar neighborhood. We actually find stars of all ages are found in the galaxy disk near the sun, young and old. The most middle disk stars could not have formed near the sun because the interstellar medium near the sun is not at metal-based. They are believed to have migrated from the inner galaxy and there are at least three ways for that to happen. Widely believed migration driven by spiral structure in this transience actually moves the stars from one circular orbit to another circular orbit at a larger areas. Next, a major event with time giving change in the asymmetric potential as possible. One such example would be the permission of the bar which would have been a big event that might have cost a lot of migration as we find in simulations. The stars can migrate as they can be trapped near Koh-rotation in the bar which can waft the stars into the solar neighborhood from the inner galaxy. Which I'll talk about in the next few slides. The motivation

behind our work is that have the super store metallicity stars to which the solar neighborhood, we are trying to examine the motions, ages and nationalities of the super solar stars look for effects that could be associated with the migration of metal which starts from the inner galaxy to the solar neighborhood. We have used data from Apogee which also started in the near infrared H band of which most of them are red giant and from Galah which observe stars are tropical weathering. The training stage contains stars which are the main sequence turn off stars. The ages of Apogee chimes are based on carbon to nitrogen ratio, calibrated on stars with Astro seismological ages. We've also used catalogs that contain data and transverse motions from Gaia. Coming to the eccentricity distribution, the orbital eccentricity near circular or elongated is a very useful indicator of stars history and it varies more strongly with a stars H. . Therefore. And to have circular orbits. That is A less than 0.15 while older stars with higher carbon density tend to have more electrical orbits. The higher it is, they have your chance is originated from the inner part of the galaxies. Next up a significant portion of the stars in the solar neighborhood. The more, 70% of these stars have low eccentricities, suggesting that they might have migrated to the solar neighborhood rather than born there. The law random motion of these stars indicates that they did not travel far from the birthplace which is at radii must larger than the solar neighborhood based on the metallicities. Here are a few of my thoughts from Galah survey. We can did with Fe/H greater than 0.1, distance from the sun less than one kiloparsec. Might have migrated from small eccentricity and support a small amount of local heating as it aged. Most of the stars and the older age group. Each suggests that there are few youngsters with these characteristics in the inner galaxy or maybe that the radial migration is not so active now it was in the past. These are some similar ones made with Apogee data for stars Fe/H greater than 0.1, the less than 0.5K PC and different radial beans. We do find in a large number of stars in the solar neighborhood in the third tunnel. Coming to the second facet of our work about Hercules, Hercules stars are actually a group of stars believed to have originated near the bars corotation radius. They are expected to be more abundant in the metal rich population and have a broad range of metallicity is similar to those found in the inner part of the galaxy. This is using data for the local neighborhood around us. The outward velocity and along my access it is the angular momentum. We see its features which is long known as the Hercules gym or moving group and can see. It's also believed that these Hercules stars are trapped in orbits around the stable point they have no particular chemical properties, but just a random collection of stars. Possible interest of Hercules through the superstore stars as defined is Hercules is also seen in the super solar stars. Here are a few of my thoughts were velocity distribution. For stars with distance from the sun less than one KPC, Fe/H greater than 0.1 and different age beans. In the top right, we can see Hercules moving similarly to the other stars in the solar neighborhood. This bottom density plot depicts the same period with this, the eccentricity force for the super solar stars are law, is consistent with radial migration and there are super solar stars in Hercules, moving similarly to the other field stars. Our future plan includes to investigate the distribution of orbital actions for the same set of stars within one KPC from the sun. Thank you so much for your attention. Ankita, you are online? If you are, we can take questions. If not, then -- never mind, okay. Great. Post in the slack and she'll answer when she can.

Benne Holwerda:

Next up is Benne Holwerda will be talking about brown dwarfs and red dwarfs and JWST and Roman period Benne: And talk about brown dwarfs a bit and JWST data. This is the motivation. Why would you can't stars if you remember from your Astro classes. Wasn't that a terrible idea at the beginning of the 20th century? If you know what you're doing, you can actually infer the shape of the Milky Way that way. You just sort of similar to in a crowd, you are in an auditorium right now and if there's more people to the left of you than to the right of you then you know you are not to the center of the room if you couldn't see the edges of the room for example. It's better to go to near infrared to employ dust issues -- avoid dust issues and the lowest possible mass for stars rather than going for the Giants or solar mass stars. You get the most common stars and you get much better statistics. Why are we doing that? Ross Ryan proposed a while ago that as these are small stars are not quite stars stop there fusion, they start cooling, they basically become a greater spectral type so the cool SAH. At the same time, this whole population gets heated. There should be a relation between spectral type and scale height. This is my summary plot of everything we knew years ago. You can see that we are mostly measuring these things is the end types and our measurements of the scale hang all over the place. It would be interesting to interesting to see how spectral type and the structure of our Milky Way is related to each other. What can you do with James Webb? It is a fantastic instrument for just about anything, but here specifically I'm going to talk about Sears collaboration and how to find the stories. We need to identify these MLTY objects. And with if possible. Can we find enough to determine the scale object. I've been at this for a while. And you get the reddish-brown points there. You can move this several orders of magnitude down. It is, this plot is sort of like a different region. You can identify stars down to 27 -- 28 magnitude. Their sources. And with Hubble, you are very happy when you get with 25. Magnitude of more discovery space here, you find a whole bunch of stellar-like objects. And we can see if we can identify what kinds of types they are from telemetry. A lot more colors from the infrared which is compared. And Roman as well has this whole suite of features. I use the SPLAT catalog for this. Take all of the possible types here and you just put down the filters and see what the bright colors look like. You can see, there are some big absorption features here, and with the latest types. These features are big enough to start affecting the filters, colors. What do local stars look like, this is the plot. This is a colors space, this is our feature space, look at it in terms of and that seems to separate out. You got the CEERS logo. They do seem to generate out quite well. I put them in numerical type, where Y is three. We want a subtype, and we want to get closer than just M or L type. So we can find a 3D structure here. What we used to do with Hubble is basically say that we have got this color coded space, here is a block, and that cut is all of the end dwarfs, does not quite translate to is contaminated because if he did not notice the scatter. You only get by broad types, and you can say it is a ML dwarf type. What do we do next? We asked the neighbors and it is based on mere's neighbor, our template space is with color space and sometimes we have got a lot of the sources, sometimes we have a few. You asked the nearest three, for example, what type they aren't, and then you have got some bright colors with some type. The one thing that you have to tune is actually see how many neighbors you have in a given space and so you can use not just a two dimensional space, multidimensional space so where Artie three data sources to the one that I'm looking at and then you can just go with the majority. And put and how many you have to find teen how many neighbors you ask. And so that works, my first go at this and you get the predictive Lee at the

bottom, true length at the Y-axis, and so you get diagonal, you try to get all of the sources on the diagonal. An optimized and trying to get within the two types subtypes. He get a pretty good data, and not too much scatter. This is very encouraging, which means I don't have to go for every single source to identify and to go for example. This visualizing, what it looks like, color-coded, two dimensional. Visualize and you have got the value and you look 20 next neighbors and you look around for the nearest neighbors. The circle become smaller if it is a more dense or training. Next one and I found a bunch of these to match late type, ground noise pretty well. There is the, I still keeping thinking of the one or two. And I know they are not exactly that, but you can use this along with the NIR cam to check on the typing, and of course the Spector comp -- machine. I got this from Sears, and there is a very neat feature Derek. We do need that in detail. And if you can do, and hopefully we can match the number count to scale height and physical type. What I found so far is that 300 to 350 PC. And the T dwarf Art parsecs. This is aligning to what we signed earlier. We are going to actually put scale height on his plot and see how much of the start information Milky Way model on the line, the response to it. And ultimately we want to figure out how many brown dwarfs are there in the Milky Way, and this goes into how many free-floating things like this are around. And that will give us the low mass, and give us the initial mass function. You get the IMF for example. IMF for the stellar halo and everything combined for all Milky Way, and that is the ultimate goal. So, Romain, can we do this with Roman. And this is the L.T. Y atmospheric models that I found. You do not really need to, and you can say that this is color coded. This is seemed to be nicely spread and they do affect where they are in the broad color space. Of course, you have got these may trick again, and he label do match up okay. You can see that this is a little thicker than I would like, this is the white paper that I submitted. You can get to within a few subtypes. I also tried this with the splat data, and that seems to spread out nicely. And the there tells me, within a few types, you can get the diagonal. Just with the broad colors from Roman, we can type MLT very well. You can set how well you want to get to different types, and as you make that bigger than your precision recall as one goes up, you can set like 80% is where I want to be. So about 0.4, better data where the filter is live. Broader, and you can use some of the information, be can definitely do it. So, the Roman benefits are that it has excellent filters. We get the statistics because it is such a wide-field instrument. The benefit that I have not talked about, but if you had recurring visits then you can actually see proper motion from galactic objects and so we can confirm that this is actually a grand dwarf, from proper nut motion, anything we can do. As an option to gift the, of these things you can separately confirm the typing. For example, I did find instances where this is a Lomas and that will be an interesting discovery. We can identify the components thickness, the halo extremes, and concerning the Lomas and for all of those components and as the Milky Way as a whole. Okay, so conclusions. Step one, what did we learn from team. There is one for T-dwarfs. We have been chipping away at this and we found a Sagittarius stream by the way. And that does pretty well. You can make it a model for example. You can get scale height and you can get the total numbers with that. They are more fields to mine here and sit at is a fun thing that you can watch. The short color spaces is where you're going to have to start classifying the sting accurately and then so you can actually find them further you can type them quickly and you can start mapping the scale height and possibly other components for free this is a free deal, but other thing you can do with Roman, JWST has a good filter suite. We are going to get a again for free. Especially, at the later types and more splat to expand that. The

wide area coverage is a very good handle on Galactic coverage, and we get this for all of the surveys. The trade-off we seek, but with the larger area means that we can get a good handle on the Milky Way, and it looks like and does ultra dwarf stars. I'm running out of voice, but I would happily take questions at this point. Thank you.

Looks like we have a question over here. Are there any online? Excellent talk, and thank you. Very interesting. My question is that you quoted with your current debt the certainty of about 0.4. About defining scales, what does that translate to? Is there an easy translation as the cooling take this long and with the uncertainties, age, something. Benne: I'm sorry. My animation is not perfect. I don't quite know, I was already very thrilled that I managed to get this down to below broad type. Essentially, we cannot get it any better than to subtypes. Honestly, so, where is it. Here it is. This is with Roman. At some point the information is not there, and so you you can't get any closer than to subtypes. How long is that, I don't quite know. And antidote in late, I know that some of these things are changing types as I rotate and then they cloud cover on the other side so they can rotate. And note from L5 to L70, something like that. Don't know if there's any scatter, and so I don't know what the actual cooling times involve. These things live a trillion years, or something like that. None of them have actually died yet, and so I would at have to ask Russ about the actual times -- type steps. Type step to teatime step is a good question. I don't know. Thank you. Let's go there. Hi. On some of the methodology that you applied. Can you go back to where you applied the selections. You said that you found most of those brown dwarfs candidates, possible that they can be -- Benne: This is when follow-up is nice. You get a probability that this is a particular brown dwarf. You saw the position and the recall, and they all sort of happy with the 80%. You never know for sure, and I should probably call them candidate dwarfs. You can always have a high chance of objects, this is how I got into it. I'm not intergalactic as trauma in her, I'm try to get rid of the sinks. We are trying to find the right color space where this thing sly and especially trying to identify and for example the long wavelength, with this particular type. The long wavelengths, that is the indication. There's all kind of exceptions and it could be for example, not just quasars, dwarf galaxies, to go for example, or we are trying to segue these things out. I can never relate out completely with telemetry. The idea that in the color space we are actually fairly confident that this is the majority of brown dwarfs. Can you provide like an estimation of wood RD magnitudes that this can be? Benne: I think of this particular plot, right. With Roman. With Roman we go to about 25 and a half. It is more Hubble like and so we can find the number densities on Skype should be similar to what we have been finding with Hubble. The typing is little bit better. With Hubble we have been finding, it is about one end dwarf. Anywhere about zero and five. It is one per minute. It is about ten times less in the elk, and then ten times less and eat T dwarf. Your mileage may vary, but you're definitely going to get one of these things at least in every minute. If you ask a spitz or about end dwarf and the deep of the galaxies, then it is a problem. Does this answer your question? This is very rough numbers and this is what we have seen from ratio. We have one really quick question over here. To identify brown dwarfs and we spent a lot of time using the paper and optimizing the parameters, and terms of metrics and determining what we are looking for. Benne: That would be great. This is also for me to play with kNN. Maximizing the information that you do have, and I hope that it is clear that we get a probability for each of the objects and you can sort of feed into a larger model of the Milky Way as a whole, so not terribly gone for the

individual sources, but the overall model sort of takes into account. That is why I'm excited that accuracy and typing is improving so that we can actually add some more components to the Milky Way construction model. It is sort of budgeting. KNN is quite powerful here. Color space. We are out of time. Any other questions? Benne: It's thank you all so much.

Nitya Kallivayalil: Near-field cosmology with Roman and JWST

She is going to be discussing near field cosmology with Roman. Nitya: You hello, and thank you so much for inviting me to get this talk. And thank you further or allow me to record this talk, I'm actually in Australia at the moment, but I hope -- there will not be time for questions and real-time, but I really look forward to seeing you all on the slack and I hope that we can have an active discussion on the slack. I'm going to be talking about near field cosmology with Roman and JWST. I will be focusing on lessons that we can take away from JWST and HST. I'm going to be speaking about two main programs, one is the results of the science program. That is P.I. with several of us as colleagues, my group in particular is working on the proper motion side of things, and also the histories. There is a lot on this plot, but I just want to highlight one thing really, which is that JWST resolves individual stars at larger distances to face a luminosity and much Crowder areas, and with higher extinction than other other facility. This is a color magnitude diagram showing a little bit about the distances and which we can reach with this facility, and it is a really exciting because everything that we know about the universe is really anchored in results are population, and how well we understand them. For example. We can do out to five mega parsecs. We can use horizontal branch out to 15 mega parsecs. And then using bright features like the tip of the red Giant branch, which actually is more luminous in the infrared than the optical that we can actually get TRGB distances out to 100 mega parsecs. This is really game changing and allows us to put our local universe where we can get really high resolution data into context for the first time with JWST we are doing it with pencil and old fashion. With Roman we can do this with launch. I'm going to be talking a little bit about HST programs that are focused on all of the dwarf galaxies associated with the Milky Way and Andromeda. This is about 400 orbits and total and I am just showing you a plot made by Eric focusing on the Milky Way sample distance and luminosity and mass on the X axis. We actually are to use HST and survey mode for these two treasury proposals and I think this is a precursor of the type of work that we can do with Roman again, which much bigger fields and getting to actually interesting statistics. In terms of an outline for the talk, I just want to focus on just a few results, and some takeaways from those results. The overarching goal of my work, our work, is to probe our model on small scales. I think this is a really fitful reteam in which to understand the nature of dark matter better. And I will talk about a project that shows, a shot in the arm with a model that is one of the predictions of the cold dark matter model is that our universe is self similar, and other where its galaxies like the LMC and LSM -- the medically way it has and a bunch of things as satellite galaxies. Can we actually prove this. I will also talk about some results from measuring histories. I will talk about the structures of these dwarf galaxies as measured from deep Hubble data and as promising probes for the nature of dark matter. I will talk about our efforts with proper motions, and that I will talk about our efforts with the stellar evolution side as well, specifically with JWST comparisons. First of all. Satellites of satellites. This is work that I've done with collaboration. And we were interested in a series of papers to

see if when the Guyette data released came out, we could identify through 6D, this will be an opportunity to measure through 3D velocity. Proper motions and velocities which were previously known for a bunch of dwarf galaxies in the vicinity of the clouds. The distances were known as well so you get full 6D information, and so you have knowledge of orbits, you can't measure things like binding energies, and make arguments as to whether objects are bound to the LSC system or the Milky Way. Set of simulations and this was like and this is using Aquarius and these are dark matter only simulations. They have extremely high resolution as he can get down to the sort of masses that galaxies the sort of dark matter and halos in which dwarf galaxies reside. In this plot you are saying, for an LMC analog benefits the mass and the known 3D velocity, and orbit of the LMC system. This is an analog from the simulation and all of these color points show dark matter that was bound to the LMC system and is falling in with the LMC system. We then went to Gaia and we measured proper motions completing the full 3D velocity space for as many dwarf galaxy candidates as we could in this general area. We found that a couple of them are actually coming in with the clouds. This is just showing an example of some of those systems for ultra dwarf galaxies. Collective centric velocities and distance. This is the X, VY, and VC. Dwarf galaxies analogues in the simulation that is coming in with the LMC, and when you expect them to fall given the LMC orbit of velocity in the space. And then the color points, blue and red actually show the measured velocity and distance of these three satellite galaxies. This is how they were identified as coming in with the LMC. And this is their past orbits over the past four billion years. Surround the Milky Way is coming in with the LMC system. And it shows that past order, shows the LMC and black, the SMC and gray, and it is wonderful to see that these past orbits actually showed these ultra galaxies so beautifully and LMC. This is great. We happen to have satellite for satellites in our vicinity and so let's see if we can push further and understandably get more about how galaxies really populate local mass dark matter and halos. This is work that is been done by Sacchi, I'm sure many of you know her and he is a graduate student who has done all of the Hubble photography for this project. We aim to measure the distance for a subset of Milky Way ultra dwarf galaxies, and LMC dwarf galaxies and these are just to bless you with some beautiful color diagrams from the systems in the paper. You can see that these are some really, really sparse systems. We are able to get into really individual star type of measurements for these galaxies. This is the result. The Y-axis is cut off a little bit, but way it is showing as the cumulative mass fraction. This is percentage of stars added as a function of look back time, and so there's a lot going on with this plot as well. Let's focus on this side. An interesting, but tantalizing at this point take away is that all of these objects that we are looking at here are extremely old and 80% of their stars are in place and these galaxies before the re-ionization which is shown in each of these panels. If you look at the means 20 subsamples, the ones that are coming in with the clouds as opposed to the ones that are Milky Way associated then the clouds mean is shown in red here, and the Milky Way mean is shown in black. I don't want to overstate this result because it is very much within errors, there is tantalizing evidence that the LMC associated dwarf galaxies are able to star up to remain the forming stars for longer than the Milky Way system. The LMC average, this population of dwarf galaxies is roughly 600 mega years younger than the Milky Way average and so LMC systems have managed for longer than Milky Way systems. This is really interesting and we haven't over interpreted this particular result yet, but we are working on it. I think that it jives with what you might expect, say for a lower density dwarfs that have been in

lower density environments for longer. I think that this is a valuable way to also probe, perhaps the re-ionization that they are actually, sort of important of the locally ionizing UV field. Let me move on then to dwarf galaxies as probes of dark matter. Specifically, we have been trying to ask some really simple questions on this front. Obviously, we are all after 3D and four density profiles for dwarf galaxies, and that is simply something that I'm very excited to pursue with Roman. However, at this point we are trying to ask simple questions, as I said, this big question of density whether dwarf galaxies their densities jives with what we would expect from cold dark matter based simulations and we have attempted to answer that here by just looking at the luminosity and half-light radius of size plane. This is work that Richstein has been leading, I just want to show one result from his work which I think is really interesting and so again there is a lot on this plot but you are looking at half-light radius on the X axis and absolute magnitude with the V band on the Y axis for a bunch of things in the Milky Way vicinity. You have cluster systems living up there, and dwarf galaxies living here. This great line here would our ultra faint dwarf galaxies, the lowest mass galaxies that are in the universe, and they have extremely high mass to light ratio, these are some of the most dark matter dominated objects that we know of in the universe they fall here. And here, and this led great you have more hazy border between the Globular galaxy system. In this particular plot we were interested to see where simulations lie and again Hannah has done a really good job at doing apples-to-apples comparison and studies are all measured and a consistent way and simulations versus NR Hubble observations. One thing that we were interested to see as do LMC dwarfs actually have the same sizes, again, these are ultra faint systems, they have the same sizes as Milky Way dwarfs. They appear to. That is interesting, I don't think that we would expect them to have different sizes, but that is also what the data is telling us. Another really interesting aspect of this plot that I am struck by is that all of these points without bars are simulated in various really interesting high-resolution dark matter simulation. The legend, and obviously, look at the slide below bit more detailed than I have time for right now. The legend here is also showing some ETHOS points, these are alternative dark matter models, sub interacting sub models that live up here and also the simulated dwarfs from the sample and FIRE they are fluffier than objects we have measured in the Milky Way vicinity does far. Other striking aspect of this plot is here already classical dwarfs of the Milky Way light, and again there are some simulation analogs with the appear as well. This entire space is quite empty in terms of observational analogs, and I don't want you to get too hung up on the number of simulated dwarfs here because we just put all of the simulation points on this plot, but on average I think that you are really expecting one analog simulation or Milky Way type galaxy here. Nonetheless, we don't have an analog and the Milky Way system, and again we can talk off-line perhaps on the slack about interesting opportunities that I see here. The only other point that I want to make in this space is that there are these predictions, right. Is it that they're predicting something that is too fluffy, but we have not found them, given incredible surface in our current surveys. These are lines of constant surface brightness, 28, 29, and his last line is 32 mag arcsec so the Roman and expected surface brightness that we can achieve. It will be interesting to see if observationally we can or cannot fill out this particular space and terms of size of dwarfs. Okay, moving on now to proper motions and so we have been trying to find ways to utilize cross observatory information because you can get long baselines, by example, combining Hubble data with JWST data. Applications with Roman, to measure proper motions, I just want to highlight a few results coming out of my group and this is work that is

being led by Jack Warfield who was a grad student at UVA. And where we measure proper motions you need an inertia reference range, something that is not moving with respect to what you're trying to measure in the foreground background galaxies are well vetted and developed by my colleague Tony to use as an inertia reference frame. And what you do is that you take an image, Starfield, background galaxy, you wait some time, you take a second image, so, this is a set of images separated by some Epoch. He measured a proper motion of the target of interest as a sort of reflex motion of these background galaxies from one Epoch to the other. Because background galaxies are to be faint and again, I don't want to get it too much into the weeds of this, but also you have to think very much about how you model them. Given a galaxy will not give you a certain level of error, but what is great about galaxies as a reference frame is that you get many of them, and typically you can get something like 100 well resolved, well measured galaxies in a given ACS MH and so you get to improve on your ultimate position for bulk proper motion and we have been developing another approach to this in our group, and this is to instead of using background galaxies to use foreground while measured Gaia stars as the inertia reference frame. In this case the Gaia stars move, background you can take as fixed. They have no measured proper motions from Gaia and so this is a relatively simple way to actually leverage the entire Gaia catalog for our purposes. This is showing that the reference moves itself, but you can measure the proper motion by removing that well measured known proper motion from Gaia from the foreground stars and this works really well for Milky Way classical dwarfs. This is showing our result 40 sculpture dwarf. Sorry, this is proper motion, and this is proper motion and the declination direction. And these are our results here compared to some other vetted results from the literature. Again, we are using Gaia foreground stars as the reference point. But between two Hubble images that were separated by a given baseline. You can see that there are in terms of classical dwarfs sculpture and Milky Way type exposure times, you get a bunch of Gaia stars that you can average over. This works really well. And this is our attempt to do this now for one of the targets of our results population program on JWST, Draco to proper motion. And it is about a six year baseline between the HST and the JWST option. What is striking here is that our result, this is the earlier result, this is from using a combination of Gaia and their own measures to add additional members from other surveys using this technique. This is a cross observatory of stars which has larger error, although it is consistent with this measurement within the areas because most of the Gaia stars, the JWST images are satellite. These are really the only stars that we have made for use that are not saturated. This is a larger issue, and this is a really easy relatively cheap technique to use to measure proper motions for any given field with-based imaging. We have to think about not saturating the reference frame, it would have to think about saturation academic strategies to do that, and this will be relevant for the moment as well. This is now and because we will not find that many Gaia stars then the we attempted to add galaxies as well. See if he can improve on our position, and what is great about the JWST filters is the combination of short and long filters actually separate stellar sources here from more extended sources and so galaxies in this cloud, and stars in the squad. If we use the color-coded information to choose like the background galaxies, and that we are still using a PSF, and at the moment to fit the center of these background galaxies and if he can just do an average then you get to add a lot of galaxies which does improve the precision, but there is still, I think a lot of work to be done in calibrating the use of these galaxies in order to do this well and we have to think about how we fit the centers, and we have to think about ways to

mitigate the fact that the sources are actually just interest and slowly looked different from optical to infrared filters and so when combining an optical and infrared image with galaxies to make a proper motion measurement, we actually have to take that into account that inertia reference frame actually looks different. They are different populations that are being highlighted and each of those filter sets. In this, and as part of that we are developing a Bayesian approach this where perhaps we can at least use the Gaia stars as a input into the fit, and also allow terms that could hone an end to this difference in methodology and with galaxies. This is work and preparation, and I just want to point out those two things. One it, we have to think about the profiles of the reference frame that we use for proper motion work, and we have to come up with ways in which way will not saturate Gaia foreground stars that could really help us in doing this with large with Roman. And finally, I think I am out of time. Let me, I have 4 minutes left. Sorry, bear with me going a little bit fast. I just want to come back to work, and this is highlighting some work done by them. They are the UVA cosmologies fellow who are working in our group. First of all, I just wanted to quickly point out a few things from some of our early release science work. This is on Globular cluster. About ten kiloparsec's and here you are looking at JWST CMD's. And I wanted to point out that this double main sequence is actually a module a and B 0. offset. So understanding CHP calibrations is actually essential to this work, but here is the hydrogen burning limit using something like Roman it you can build the full spatial extent of Globular in clusters. You can go down to the hydrogen burning limit and explore things like gradients and binary stars and multiple populations. This is now W LM, and this is in our focus as far ERS work. This is showing some really exciting work on staff histories led by Kristi's work and also by Chris at UVA. This is WLM field. You can see the highlight radius of WLM and where we have coverage by HST and JWST overlap. And the first point to make is that Roman can provide deep CMD's for entire galaxies and things like population gradients for example with and without this half-light radius will be key for testing feedback on Galaxy simulations and understanding coupling between ions and dark matter. The great thing about this work is that this is showing you a history for this field of overlap between ACS and near camp. The take away is that this agreement is great using ACS with well vetted techniques and near cam which we now need -- and the infrared but that has been working really well really good agreement recovered by the ACS field using the Nir field, this is using Chris's work using the JWST and Nir camera. And data minus model in his final color here. And again, this modular that he has been working on should be available and ready to use by the public in the not-too-distant future and and my talk here very quickly with these takeaways the universe we have found ultra faint dwarf galaxies as a promising frontier and testing feedback models and that a luminosity size plan that my plane is a good space to understand whether we are producing realistic dwarf galaxies and this will be really enabled and a huge way with Roman, and proper motions. We are utilizing observations, and we will play a key role in a expanding the number of available Gaia stars. It is a really powerful tool that we have to make and this is a way to measure a proper motion and every field. Population gradients and again coupling between dark matter and ions is going to be done with larch at Roman, and we proved that stellar evolution libraries and their sensitivity and accuracy are working well in the near IR filters and relation to the optical filters, and I will stop there. Thank you so much for your attention. I look forward to hearing from you on the slack. Enjoy the conference. That concludes session three. Quick thanks to all of the speakers. Now we will begin session four.

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